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Overview of Django web application framework for Python

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ABSTRACT

Django is an open source web application framework for python. This framework is an architectural pattern that separates an application into three main logical components which are Model, View and Templates. Usually any other framework relies on model, view and controller but in django we see the templates instead of controller. We all know through these features we can get clear idea of UI logic, Business logic and Input logic for application development Django frame work includes ORM (object Relational Mapping) libraries that allows developers to work with database records as object in application code rather than writing sql queries. Django also provides middleware components that allow developers to add functionalities to the request –responses cycle such as logging, catching user handling. Most important component in Django framework is template engine that allows developers to generate dynamic HTML content by combing static HTML template with data from application.

Keywords: *Django, frame work, Python application, model*

1. INTRODUCTION

In Django there is tool name called Django evolution which ensures how to handle changes to database schema in project so we can say its best alternative for already built in django migration tool. with django evolution, you can define database changes manually and more importantly its very helpful when migrating from older version of django .

What as i said by beginning of introduction django has been categorised into three main logical components which are model,view and templates so now I would like to take a brief on View components.

VIEW: It's a python function that takes web request and returns a web response. This response can be a HTML content of Webpage or Redirect or XML doc or 404 error or image.so view used to create webpage for creating along with view we need url.Here each view has to be mapped with corresponding url pattern and this going to be done via a module url config.

2. DESCRIPTION

When user makes a request for a page on your webapp.Django controller takes over a look for corresponding view via url.py file and then return a html response. In url.py file the most important thing is url patterns tuples it's a where you define mapping between url & views.

- Function based views are written using function in python which receives as an argument HTTP Request object & returns an HTTP Response.
- Class Based views provide an alternative way to implement views as python object instead of function. They don't replace function based views

Fig. 1: working of view in django

Template: another field used in django for development of application. In django template is basically written in HTML, CSS, & javascript in .html file. django mainly function with backend so in order to provide a frontend and layout to website we use templates itself.

There are two ways to use templates first one is “use of the simple template directory which will spread all over the project” and second is “use of different directory”.

Django makes it possible to separate python and HTML, python goes in views and HTML goes in template. To link these two, Django relies on the render function and django template language. Render function takes three parameters which are Request, Path to Template and Dictionary of Parameters.

In django some basic template tags and filters are available through these tags we can perform programming logics like if statement and for loops statements. So here ‘if’ and ‘for’ keywords are template tags and these are surrounded by curly braces with percentile notation. For eg: {% if x=1% } or for(% y==0% }.actually django provide more numbers of tags to perform logic and some of are commonly uses which are

[comment,cycle,debug,for,if,include,load,now,url,csrf_token,extends etc].

Django also provide django filters these filters are used to transform the values of from django .db.import models

```
class Employee(models.Model):
    first_name
    =models.CharField(max_length=10)
    last_name
    =models.CharField(max_length=15)
```

the above model will create a table into database

```
CREATE TABLE employee(
“first_name” varchar(15) NOT NULL,
“last_name” varchar(10) NOT NULL,
)
```

variables and tag arguments. We know tag cant modify values of variables whereas filter can be used for incrementing values of variables or modifying it to ones own need.filters can be chained the output of one filter is applied to another so we have standard syntax for filters I,e

```
{{variable_name | filter_name}}
```

We have some list of filters which are given below bracket

```
[add,addslash,capfirst,cut,date,default,join,first,makelist,slice,time,upper]
```

After the django template our next area to focus on application development using django framework is Model. In MVT design pattern model is more essential part of framework the main function of model is simply the task and organize the tables into models, so each model is map to single database table. So usally in mind question will raises that what the model actually consist?

Model actually consist a python class and subclass and attribute representation using database so model used to create and interact with a corresponding database table for storing model objects by this definition we can say django model is subclass of django.db.models.Model and each field of the model class represents a database fields or table. Let see simple example of creating model name “employee”

After creating new fields we must create and apply migrations by given following commands

- **Python manage.py makemigrations**
- **Python manage.py migrate**

To select and delete the objects in django we have a queryset through this we can select objects in various ways. Commands for selecting all objects in django is

- **All_Objects = MyModel.objects.all()**
- For single objects command is
- **Single_Objects=MyModel.objects.get(attribute=value)**

Similarly to delete an a object the command is

- `Single_Object = MyModel.objects.get(attribute=value)`
`Single_Objects.delete()`

3. CONCLUSION

- Usually any other framework rely on model, view and controller but in django we see the templates instead of controller
- VIEW, It's a python function that takes web request and returns a web response. This response can be a HTML content of Webpage or Redirect or XML doc or 404 error or image.
- There are two ways to use templates first one is "use of the simple template directory which will spread all over the project" and second is "use of different directory".
- Function based views are written using function in python which recives as an argument HTTP Request object & returns an HTTP Response
- After the django template our next area to focus on application development using django framework is Model
- Model actually consist a python class and subclass and attribute representation using database so model used to create and interact with a corresponding database table for storing model objects by this definition we can say django model is subclass of `django.db.models`

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